
Conservation of Natural Resources and The Protection of Endangered Species in Nigeria: A Roadmap to Socio Economic Development

A.O. Adeniyi¹, A. O. Akanle²

¹Department of Jurisprudence and International Law Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti

²Department of Public Law Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti

ABSTRACT

The abundance of natural resources in a country significantly enhances its wealth and supports economic growth. Natural resources cannot fulfill their optimal function in economic development if not managed sustainably. The environment encompasses the habitat of humans, plants and animals including air, water, vegetation, flora, fauna and the overall ecosystem. Nigeria is an ecologically distinctive nation with a diverse array of ecosystems. This ecosystem include coastal and mangrove swamps, lowland montane forests and grassland savannahs, comprising three principal forest types and seven vegetation zones throughout the country. The study therefore carried out an appraisal of environmental laws for the protection of natural resources with specific objectives to examine the types of natural resources, importance of conservation of natural resources, methods of conserving natural resources for the purpose of achieving sustainable development and applicability of international framework with the aim of achieving goal 8 and 12 of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. To achieve this, the study adopted a desk-based research methodology and examined the existing international and domestic environmental laws for the protection and conservation of natural resources. The study concluded that although the exploitation of natural resources is essential for economic development, it is quite unfortunate that exploitation of these resources brings about a lot of negative effect to the environment, which includes deforestation, erosion, pollution and loss of biodiversity. The study therefore made recommendations to improve the sustainable use of natural resources by harnessing resources in a manner that will not imperil the environment but improve income generation of the nation.

KEYWORDS: Conservation, Natural resources, Endangered Species, flora, fauna, economic development

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's ecology has suffered from human exploitation, just like other national environments. The age of industrialisation will always be significant in human history because, among other things, it signaled the start of human activity's destruction of the environment. Industries freely contaminated the environment and disrupted the ecology in their pursuit of economic and social progress. Wasteful land clearing for the construction of schools and industries, overuse of marine resources and wildlife, and industrial machinery releasing toxic chemicals like chlorinated hydrocarbons into the atmosphere have all occurred in nearly every nation. Nigeria is endowed with a wide variety of wild plant and animal species that are adequate to fulfill the country's goals for sustainable development. The potential of nature in a particular area to offer a variety of regulatory functions, such as life cycle maintenance and habitat and gene pool conservation, is reflected in the species richness and animal diversity.

Every day, anthropogenic forces specifically, people endanger Nigeria's wild flora and animals in their quest for the necessities of life, such as clothing, food and shelter. In addition to the fact that the resources are exploited carelessly without any deliberate attempt to replace them, the woods that serve as their habitat and repository are invaded for socioeconomic purposes. The threat to the species persists because, in addition to the insufficiency of the legislative framework for the conservation of wild fauna and flora, the current laws and treaties are not properly enforced. Due to the regulatory bodies' apparent lack of infrastructure, intruders are causing havoc in the woodlands where the species lives. The difficulties seem substantial and require comprehension

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for effective resolution via the examination of the legal framework. This paper examines the conceptual framework, protection of endangered species and sustainable development, impact of conservation of natural resources on socioeconomic development. The methodology adopted in this article is doctrinal, drawing upon primary and secondary sources of information in existing relevant legislations, treaties, conventions, agreements and protocols. The paper is concluded with recommendations.

2.0 UNDERSTANDING THE CONCEPT OF CONSERVATION OF NATURAL RESOURCES

Natural resources are intended for human utilisation, although they must be employed in a manner that safeguards the different species of flora, fauna and ecosystems for the benefit of current and future generations. The International Union for the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources defined conservation as the management of human use of the biosphere so that it may yield the greatest sustainable benefit while maintaining its potential to meet the needs and aspirations of future generations.¹ Conservation entails the sustainable management and utilisation of natural resources to avert their exploitation, annihilation or degeneration.² According to Black's Law Dictionary, conservation is the supervision, management and maintenance of natural resources, the protection, improvement and use of natural resources for the highest social as well as economic benefits. Natural resources encompass any energy source, organism or material occurring in nature that is utilised by humans. They are biophysical substances that fulfill human needs and contribute directly to human well-being.³ Conservation of natural resources in essence is the preservation or protection of plants, animals, mountains, natural areas from the damaging effect of human activity as a result of neglect or over-exploitation.

3.0 ENDANGERED SPECIES OF WILD FLORA AND FAUNA IN NIGERIA

International collaboration is crucial for safeguarding specific species of wildlife and plants from over-exploitation via global commerce. Species means any species, subspecies or geographically separate population thereof.⁴ An endangered species is any species that faces the threat of extinction due to a rapid decline in its population or the destruction of its essential habitat.⁵ While many hazards arise naturally, the majority are attributable to human actions and their economic and cultural initiatives. For ecosystems and floristic diversity to function properly, wild fauna with a variety of species compositions is essential. The potential of nature in a particular area to offer a variety of regulatory functions, such as life cycle maintenance and habitat and gene pool conservation, is reflected in the species richness and animal diversity.⁶

Nigeria is blessed with rich array of wild species of flora and fauna that are sufficient to support the aspirations for sustainable development. Anthropogenic induced forces and specifically human beings in the search for the basic needs of life viz. food, clothing and shelter daily endanger the wild fauna and flora in Nigeria. It is ironic that Nigeria is still among the world's poorest nations while having an abundance of wild plants and animals. Malaysia visited Nigeria in the early 1960s in search of honeybees and palm seedlings.⁷ In Nigeria today, there is no pragmatic policy for the protection of the wild species of palm trees as the palm trees are uprooted in some parts of Nigeria for tapping palm wine without any concerted effort at replacement. There is no denying that a large chunk of Nigeria's wildlife resources is extinct. Eagles, rhinoceroses (the last of which was killed in the 1950s before Yankari became a game reserve), dinosaurs, sabre-toothed cats, dodo, woolly mammoths, ground sloths, golden toads, star sea cows, Tasmanian tigers, passenger pigeons, great auks, white dolphins and more are among the animals that are in danger of going extinct.⁸ There are 189 plants on the Nigerian red list, of which 138 are vulnerable, 18 are endangered, 16 are severely at low risk and 1 specie is classified as having insufficient data.⁹ The top endangered species includes; Baobab tree, Monkey puzzle, Dragon Tree, Bois Dentelle, Venus Fly Trap, Underground Australian Orchid, Cork, Rafflesia, Welwitschia Mirabilis, Green Pitcher Plant, Titan Arum and Baseball Plant.

¹ R. D. Schwass, 'World Conservation Strategy of the International Union for the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources' Encyclopedia of Life Support Systems available at www.eolss.net accessed 19 January 2026.

² A. Trivedi & S. Agniwanshi, 'Conservation of Natural Resources' (2024) 11 (5) *Internatinal Journal of Fauna and Biological Studies* 23.

³ A. O. Ayeni & J. Y. Fashagba, 'Natural Resources: Distribution, Governance and Politics' (2018) 381 available at www.ir.unilag.edu.ng accessed 19 January 2026.

⁴ Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora 1973, art 1.

⁵ H. Dublin, 'Endangered Species' (2026) available at www.britannica.com accessed 22 January 2026.

⁶ D. U. Hooper *et.al*, 'Effects of Biodiversity on Ecosystem Functioning: A Consensus of Current Knowledge' (2005) 75 (1)*Ecological Monographs* 5.

⁷ O. Oni, 'Establishment of Oil Palm Plantation' (2016) available at www.businessday.ng accessed 22 January 2026.

⁸ M. A. Idowu & O. A. Morenikeji, 'Wild Fauna Conservation in Nigeria' (2015) 3 (3) *Environment and Natural resources Research*.

⁹ A. O. Isichei, 'Endangered Plants in Nigeria: Time for a New Paradigm for Vegetation Conservation' available at www.researchgate.net accessed 23 January 2026.

4.0 IMPORTANCE AND METHODS OF CONSERVATION OF NATURAL RESOURCES

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) promoted the need to preserve nature and natural resources. The ecology of plants and animals in Nigeria has been critically endangered to the point of extinction. For the human race to survive, natural resource conservation is essential.¹⁰ The rapid depletion of limitless natural resources is a result of growing human environment interaction brought about by scientific and technological advancements. To help society fulfill present and future needs, it is crucial to manage natural resources and employ conservation strategies.¹¹

Promoting sustainability is another crucial component of conservation. Conservation aids in ensuring that established ecosystems and natural resources are managed in a way that permits their sustainable use without deteriorating them or jeopardizing their capacity to support future generations.¹² A sustainable future and the preservation of the natural balance depend on conservation. It is crucial for maintaining species and ecosystems, safeguarding natural resources and advancing sustainability. Ecosystems offer a multitude of ecosystem services, such as controlling the climate, supplying resources necessary for human subsistence and cleaning the air and water.¹³ The availability of recreational facilities is guaranteed by the conservation of natural resources. Natural resource conservation is essential to a country's economic growth because the unequal distribution of natural resources in Nigeria's geo-political zones boosts tourism. The habitats of these species such as forests, mountains water bodies etc. are beautiful scenes to behold, hence tourists are always attracted because of the wonders of nature in the locations. In Nigeria, the Yankari Game reserves in Bauchi State, Obudu Resorts in Cross River State, Old Oyo Park in Oyo State etc. are tourist attraction centers in Nigeria because of the species of plants and animals.

In addition, the preservation of natural resources advances and supports scientific advancement. The practice of orthodox and traditional medicine is entirely dependent on natural resources. Research on technology and medicine will be challenging without the preservation of natural resources.¹⁴ The preservation of habitats and ecosystems is essential for the survival of numerous plant and animal species and for sustaining the fragile equilibrium of the natural world. From an economic standpoint, the world's economy is mostly driven by natural resources. Natural resources are essential to the development of many industries including mining, forestry, agriculture and fishing. We can guarantee these industries' long-term viability by safeguarding these resources.¹⁵ Some animals depend on other animals for survival, for instance, carnivorous animals like Lion, Tiger; Bears etc depends on other animals for survival. In essence, the extinction of these animals equates to loss of food by the carnivorous which will eventually lead to their death.

In other to conserve natural resources in line with goal 12 of the United Nations sustainable development goals to be achieved by the year 2030, it is essential that the method of conservation be discussed. The methods are discussed as follows;

- a) **Forest Conservation Methods:** numerous vital materials found in forests are vital to preserving ecological balance and generating economic gains. With an estimated 3.5% yearly deforestation, Nigeria's forests are seriously threatened.¹⁶ Citizens should be made to plant two or more trees when one is cut. Afforestation will not only aid conservation but also mitigate erosion caused by wind and water. Additionally, it serves as a home for birds and other symbiotic plants and aids in the maintenance of the environment. By lowering human pressures and improving landscape connectivity and fragmentation, afforestation also aids forests in adapting to climate change.¹⁷
- b) **Water Conservation Methods:** water conservation strategies, such as rainwater collection, drip irrigation and switching to water-efficient fixtures is to help in the conservation of water for future use. In essence, rainwater collection is the process of gathering rainwater from building roofs and storing it beneath for later use.¹⁸ Better irrigation practices to reactivate areas that lack clean and drinkable water. People should continue to practice the habits of shutting off the faucets when not in use and spending less time in the shower, both of which contribute to water conservation. Reusing some water is also crucial for

¹⁰ W. A. Adebayo, *Contemporary Issues in International Environmental Law* (Ekiti State University Press, 2017)

¹¹ P. Tiwari & N. Kumari, 'Importance of Conservation and Management of Natural Resources in Today's World' www.researchgate.net accessed 3 March 2026.

¹² V. S. Lal, 'The Importance of Conservation: Protecting our Natural Resources and Biodiversity for a Sustainable Future' (2022) 10 (1) *Research Reviews: Journal of Ecology and Environmental Sciences* 4.

¹³ K. Elon, 'Conservation of Ecosystem and its Diversity of Policies, Challenges' (2023) 13 (9) *Journal of Environmental and Occupational Health* 1.

¹⁴ W. A. Adebayo (n10) p 80.

¹⁵ Blazingprojects, 'Importance of Conservation of Natural Resources' (2026) www.blazingprojects.com accessed 3 March 2026.

¹⁶ O. S. Areo, 'Modern Forest Operation Techniques in Nigeria: Challenges and Solutions' (2023) 7 (2) *Australian Journal of Science and Technology* 76.

¹⁷ Climate Adapt, 'Afforestation and Reforestation as Adaptation Opportunity' (2024) www.adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata accessed 30 March 2026.

¹⁸ M. Kumari & J. Singh, 'Water Conservation: Strategies and Solutions' (2016) 1 (4) *International Journal of Advanced Research and Review* 75

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watering our homes' gardens.¹⁹ Sewage and industrial waste must be treated before being discharged into waterways. These effluents' direct discharge into bodies of water causes severe water contamination and is detrimental to the ecosystem.²⁰

- c) **Soil Conservation Methods:** soil can be conserved in order to reduce erosion by using agronomic techniques which includes terracing, contour farming and cover crops as practiced by our ancestors which helps in greater agricultural produce. Crop rotation is the practice of growing different types of crops in the same area across a season.²¹
- d) **Practice of In-Situ and Ex-Situ Conservation of Wildlife:** *in-situ* meaning on site involves protecting plants and animals in their native environments. They include places like parks, biosphere reserves and wildlife sanctuaries among others while *ex-situ* on the other hand, refers to the preservation of plants and animals away from their original environments. Pollen banks, DNA banks, zoos, seed banks, botanical gardens and tissue culture banks are a few examples of this.²²

5.0 SOURCES OF DANGER TO ANIMAL AND PLANTS SPECIES IN NIGERIA

Wild species of fauna and flora, as previously noted, provide countless advantages to humans, plants, animals and the ecosystem. The scientific advancement in conventional and alternative medicine is facilitated by research on the significance of wildlife. The sources of danger to wildlife in Nigeria are:

- a) **Hunting and Poaching:** in many regions of Nigeria, particularly in rural areas, hunting is seen as a vocation, often serving as a traditional family occupation.²³ Hunting is one source of danger to wildlife existence. Professional hunters receive accolades and are bestowed with chieftaincy titles for their exploits and skill in hunting wildlife. Competent hunters are categorized based on the size of the animals they hunt, such as elephants, lions, buffalo etc.²⁴ Numerous animal species will become extinct due to excessive hunting, as has already occurred across the nation. The perception of the people in the traditional communities and generally in Nigeria to wildlife has constituted a grave danger to the survival of wildlife.

The effects of poaching on wildlife are disastrous. Sometimes it's the main factor that puts an animal in danger of going extinct. Between 2014 and 2017, around 100,000 African elephants were murdered for their ivory.²⁵ Poaching frequently coexists with other crimes like corruption and money laundering, and it has been connected to armed militia organisations in Africa especially Nigeria (activities of cattle rustlers) that are suspected of trafficking ivory to finance their activities and kidnapping of citizens for same purpose. Additionally, poached animals can spread diseases like Ebola.²⁶

- b) **Overpopulation and Industrialisation:** more people may encroach on Nigeria's wild animal and plant ecology due to the country's growing human population and industries. It has been observed that Fulani herdsmen that move from the northern part to the southern part of Nigeria have caused a lot of habitat degradation by cutting down trees to provide their animals with food. The Fulani herders' practices of encroaching on protected areas and aggressively opposing any attempt to remove their livestock from them are still in place in the country today. For continued human existence, more people need more food, water, energy and other resources. As a result of this, it is difficult to maintain the current way of life before overpopulation as things become more and more scarce as a result of higher population.

- c) **Deforestation:** wild animals require appropriate habitat, or places where they can live comfortably, safely and securely. These spaces are used by them for hiding, feeding, reproducing, sleeping, resting and avoiding predators. However, animals lose access to vital supplies and are exposed to new dangers when we disturb these places by cutting down trees.²⁷ Animal species endangered by forest loss may also be more vulnerable to being slaughtered by predators that have lost their natural habitat. Therefore, deforestation have direct and indirect effects on animal and plant species, which is, a decline in population and an increased chance of extinction.²⁸

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

²⁰ S. S. Jagannath, 'Water Conservation and its Methodology' (2017) 9 (1) *International Journal of Management & IT* 1

²¹ K. Nithinkumar & A. Gairola, 'Soil Conservation Methods: Agronomic Measures and Vegetative Barriers' (2023) 2 (9) *The Agriculture Magazine* 236

²² T. Saaondo & O. Olasan, 'Ex-Situ and In-Situ Conservation of Plant Genetic Resources in Nigeria' (2023) www.scienceopen.com/document/file/6765d1a6-f55c accessed 30 March 2026.

²³ M. A. Idowu & O. A. Morenikeji, 'Wild Fauna Conservation in Nigeria' (2015) 5 (3) *Environment and Natural resources Research* 104.

²⁴ J. A. Fa, S. M. Funk & R. Nasi, 'Hunting Wildlife in the Tropics and Subtropics' (2022) www.e-space.mmu.ac.uk/63024/7/hunting accessed 6 March 2026.

²⁵ J. Hall, 'Poaching Animals Explained' (2019) www.nationalgeographic.com accessed 7 March 2026.

²⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁷ T. Bodo, B. G. Gimah & K. J. Seomoni, 'Deforestation: Human Causes, Consequences and Possible Solutions' (2021) 4 (2) *Journal of Geographical Research* 24

²⁸ T. G. Ranjan, 'Global Deforestation and its Relation to Animal Extinction' (2022) 15 (1) *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews* 507

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- d) **Exploration and Exploitation of Natural Resources:** Apart from agriculture, oil and solid minerals are vital to the economic growth in Nigeria. The discovery of crude oil in Nigeria in 1958 and the subsequent commercial production had positive influence on the economy of Nigeria and the same caused environmental degradation in the oil producing communities. The Niger Delta region of Nigeria has suffered significant environmental harm as a result of oil drilling. The exploitation of wild species encompasses both non-lethal practices like gathering wild fish for aquarius or gathering fruit and flowers, as well as lethal practices like cod fishing and tree cutting. It does not include the exploitation of non-living resources or the usage of domestic animals.²⁹ The effects of oil spills are particularly concerning since they affect aquatic biodiversity and so constitute a serious threat to aquatic ecosystems, including coastal areas.³⁰
- e) **Terrorism:** livestock production is essential to the lives of numerous households in the developing countries and significantly contributes to the availability of food and nutrition in the society. Terrorism is the foremost peril to Nigeria's agricultural communities, resulting in grave repercussions for food production.³¹ Boko Haram and the Islamic State of West Africa have devastated the northeastern region of Nigeria, displacing several farmers and destroying their agricultural land through fire set by bandits on farmlands.³² The presence of terrorists in the forests has substantially transformed the landscape, rendering wild animal species vulnerable to indiscriminate killing.
- f) **Agriculture and Fish Farming:** due to habitat degradation, pollution, overexploitation, agriculture and fishing are significant contributors to the loss of biodiversity, endangering thousands of plant and animal species. Prior to the discovery of crude oil in the late 1950s, Nigeria's economy was based primarily on agriculture. One of the causes of the invasion of Nigeria's forest areas for farming is the country's spiraling population expansion without a commensurate increase for land accessible for cultivation.³³ Another factor endangering marine life is the way local fish breeder's fish. When fish farmers utilize explosives or hazardous chemicals, marine life becomes a victim of ecoterrorism.³⁴
- g) **Invasion of Alien Species:** invasion by species results in significant effects on the habitats they infiltrate, including impacts on indigenous species diversity, alterations in soil nutrient composition, modifications of forest fire cycles and a decline in the productivity of the invaded ecosystems. Invasion can be either anthropogenic or natural.³⁵ Fish farming, pet trading, horticulture and biocontrol are just a few examples of the intentional introduction of species. Unintentionally, species are introduced by land and water transportation, travel and scientific research. The invasion of alien species have contributed directly to the extinction of many species of wildlife including birds, reptiles, invertebrates etc. additionally, invasions by bacteria of alien plants are known to have significant effect on agricultural crops and the human economy.³⁶

6.0 INTERNATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE CONSERVATION OF NATURAL RESOURCES

Conservation of natural resources is important to the welfare and survival of human race. It is a design to achieve sustainable development. In the 1960s, problems such as soil erosion, air and water pollution was in existence, therefore the need for conservation of resources became necessary and this awoken the government and people in all parts of the world especially in the industrialized countries. This brought about the United Nations conference on human environment, which was held in Stockholm in June 1972 to tackle problems facing the environment. The legal include but not limited to the following:

- a. **African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources:** the convention provides that parties shall ensure that conservation and management of natural resources are treated as an integral part of national or local development plans.³⁷ In essence, conservation of natural is essential for economic development of a nation.

²⁹ T. C. N. Angaye & K. E. Lelei, 'The Impacts of Resource Exploitation in the Niger Delta: Highlighting the Urgent Need for Biodiversity Conservation' (2022) www.sciencedirect.com accessed 16 March 2026.

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ O. Fadare, G. Zanello & C. Srinivasan, 'The Joint Effects of Terrorism and Land Access on Livestock Production Decisions : Evidence from Northern Nigeria' (2023) www.sciencedirect.com accessed 16 March 2026

³² A. D. Owenorisiede, 'Islamic State of West Africa Province (ISWAP) and the Resurgence of Terrorism in Nigeria: Security and Socio-economic Implications' (2023) 1 (1) *Journal of Political Discourse* 112

³³ T. S. G. Apata, 'Linkages Between Crude –Oil Exploration and Agricultural Development in Nigeria: Implications for Relevant Qualitative Data Collection and analysis to Improve Rural economy' (2024) www.fao.org accessed 16 March 2026

³⁴ R. F. Olaniyan, 'Fishing Methods and their Implications for a Sustainable Environment' (2015) 6 (3) *Fisheries and Aquaculture Journal* 3

³⁵ K. S. Dogra *et al.*, 'Alien Plant Invasion and their Impact on Indigenous Species Diversity at Global Scale: A Review (2010) 2 (9) *Journal of Ecology and the Natural Environment* 176

³⁶ K. Najberek *et al.* 'Effects of invasive Alien Species on Native Plant Diversity and Crop Yield' (2024) 13 (6) www.mdpi.com accessed 16 March 2026

³⁷ African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources, 1968, art 14 (1) (a)

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- b. **Convention on Biological Diversity:** The Convention was opened for signature during the Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil on 5 June, 1992 and by the end of July 1993, 165 countries had signed the treaty. The Convention is based on a broad ecosystem approach rather than on a specific species or ecosystem or site basis, which characterizes other international conservation agreements. Nigeria signed the Convention on 13 June, 1992 and ratified it on 29 August 1994. Nigeria has implemented some of the provisions of the Convention especially the provision that requires the conservation in-situ. This Nigeria has done through the enactment of legal frameworks such as the Forestry laws in many states of the federation, the National Parks Act which resulted in the establishment of the National Parks Basin, such as Kainji, Lake Chad Basin, Cross River, Gashaka-Gumti and old Oyo National Parks.
- c. **Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora:** the convention provides that state shall take measures to protect wild fauna and flora and prohibit trade in the same and the convention recognized the need for the protection of certain species of wild fauna and flora against over-exploitation through trade.³⁸
- d. **United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change:** Climate change is intrinsically related to biodiversity management. The warming of the earth's environmental may adversely affect natural ecosystems and humankind is far reaching. Changes in temperature may affect the growth of trees and animal lives. The effect of climate change on the Lake Chad basin is the shrinking of the lake with the consequence of reduction in space for habitation for the marine living resources.³⁹ The convention provides that parties should cooperate in preparing for adaptation to the impacts of climate change, develop and elaborate appropriate and integrated plans for coastal zone management of water resources and agriculture and for the protection and rehabilitation of areas particularly in Africa. Places affected by drought and desertification as well as floods.⁴⁰
- e. **United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS):** the UNCLOS is the most comprehensive Convention in public international law that addresses a variety of maritime laws and is designed to regulate the use of oceans for mining, commerce, fishing, exploration and navigation.⁴¹ The Convention was adopted in 1982. It establishes guidelines for all uses of the oceans and their resources and establishes a complete regime of law and order throughout the world's seas and oceans.⁴²

7.0 LEGAL MEASURES FOR CONSERVATION OF NATURAL RESOURCES IN NIGERIA

The Nigerian environment is made up of diverse bodies of water. The marine living resources have been threatened and exposed to different hazards as a result of the activities of human. The forest have been destroyed by the activities of dare-devils carrying out criminal activities by way of setting fire into the forest after kidnapping operations to derail the security agencies from following them. The legal instruments for conservation of natural resources in Nigeria are as follows;

- a) **Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999, as Amended):** The Nigerian Constitution's supremacy clause establishes it as the fundamental legal authority in Nigeria⁴³. This overarching legal authority underscores that any actions, policies, or laws on environmental protection are ultimately derived from and must align with the Constitution. However, the Constitution only indirectly addresses environmental concerns, particularly in Chapter II, which focuses on the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy. Chapter II of the Constitution states that the State shall protect and improve the environment and safeguard Nigeria's water, air, land, forest, and wildlife.⁴⁴ The Constitution also provides that the exploitation of human or natural resources in any form whatsoever for the reasons other than the good of the community shall be prevented.⁴⁵
- b) **National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) Act, 2007:** The importance of environmental protection has become increasingly recognised in Nigeria, where industrial growth and urbanization have often brought severe environmental consequences, including air, water, and land pollution. The Nigerian government, in response, enacted the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) Act in 2007, establishing

³⁸ Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora, 1973, art iv, v

³⁹ Y. Li, 'Shallow Dive: The Data behind the Impacts of Lake Chad's Shrinkage' (2024) www.blogs.worldbank.org accessed 30 March 2026

⁴⁰ United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, art 4(e)

⁴¹ A. Ahmad, 'International Law of the Sea: An Overlook and Case Study' (2017) 8 *Beijing Law Review* 23

⁴² J.N. Popi and M. Z. Alamgir and W. H. Kutubuddin, 'The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea: The State of Compliance in Bangladesh' (2024) 7 (1) *BMJ* 184

⁴³ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999, s.1

⁴⁴ *Ibid*, s. 20

⁴⁵ *Ibid*, s. 17 (2) (d)

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NESREA as a critical regulatory agency tasked with environmental protection and pollution control across Nigeria. The Act empowers the agency to ensure the conservation of natural resources in Nigeria.⁴⁶

- c) **The Sea Fisheries Act**⁴⁷: It provides for the control, regulation and protection of sea fisheries in the territorial waters of Nigeria. The Act prohibits the killing of fish by the use of any explosive or noxious substances.⁴⁸
- d) **The Federal National Parks Act**⁴⁹: the Act is responsible for the preservation and protection of wild animals and plants and other vegetation in national park. The Act provides for the permanent preservation, to the greatest possible extent, of species and protect and preserve its cultural and natural resources and values and ensure that its use shall be nature-based and ecologically sustainable.⁵⁰
- e) **Animal Diseases (Control) Act**: The Act makes provision for measures to prevent the spreading of diseases affecting animals in Nigeria.⁵¹ It places restriction on the importation of animals, hatching eggs, poultry, any vaccine serum, toxin, antitoxin, antibody and antigen used in veterinary practice and infectious agents.
- f) **Harmful Waste Special Criminal Provision**⁵²-the act is to prohibit the carrying, depositing and dumping of harmful waste on any land, territorial waters of Nigeria. The Act addresses the disposal and management of harmful waste within Nigeria. It criminalizes the unlawful disposal, transportation, or processing of harmful waste materials. This provision is aimed at ensuring that harmful waste is disposed of in a manner that does not harm the environment or public health⁵³. Illegal disposal of harmful waste can result in severe environmental degradation. For example, toxic substances dumped into water bodies can lead to contamination of drinking water sources, harming local populations and wildlife.

8.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Trade is not the only factor endangering wild plants and animals. Cultural customs in Nigeria have become into endangered species' albatross. Every day wildlife species are targeted for bush using traps, snares, explosives or dane guns. Even among the wealthy, there is an uncontrollably high demand for wildlife species. Because life depends on the biosphere's ability to function properly, conservation is crucial to human survival. Its ultimate goal is to keep the biosphere in a healthy state. Nigeria's wildlife species, both plant and animals, have not been adequately protected; as a result, some of them have been exploited to the point of extinction and others are regularly degraded. The legal measures are adequate, but several treaties have not yet been domesticated. The conservation of natural resources is essential as that is how to guarantee their sustainable use for future generations as well as for those who are alive today. Nigeria's wild plant and animal species are in a vile and unstable state. The fact that many of these species are completely absent from both natural and manmade environments serves as evidence of this.

Every day, wild plants and animals are in danger, and some have been either extinct or moved to safer areas in another jurisdiction. It is therefore recommended that government should implement laws strictly in order to show that they are committed to protecting the species. National orientation regarding the importance of species to enhance socio-economic development should be made known. It is also important that the government of Nigeria ratify international treaties and conventions on the protection and conservation of wild plant and animals. The habit of setting bush on fire should be brought to an end. Habitat protection is the key to protecting our rare, threatened and endangered species and an advantage to economic growth of the nation. Lastly, there is a need for Nigeria to adopt a legislative framework for the defence of animal rights, following in the footsteps of developed nations like the United Kingdom, United States of America and Kenya in Africa and host of others.

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⁴⁶ National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) Act, 2007, s. 7 (c), (e).

⁴⁷ Cap S4 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004

⁴⁸ *ibid*, s. 1

⁴⁹ Cap N65, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004.

⁵⁰ *ibid*, s. 26 (a-c)

⁵¹ Animal Diseases (Control) Act, 2022, s. 20

⁵² Cap H1 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004

⁵³ Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provision) Act, s. 2

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- 4) Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora 1973, art 1.
- 5) Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora, 1973, art iv, v
- 6) Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provision) Act, s. 2
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- 9) The Sea Fisheries Act, 2004
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